

Spectrophotometric determination of ezetimibe in pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : Ezetimibe is chemically 1-(4-fluorophenyl)-3(R)-[3-(4-fluorophenyl)-3(S)-hydroxypropyl]-4(S)-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone. It is a selective cholesterol absorption inhibitor. A simple, sensitive, accurate, rapid and economical spectrophotometric method is developed, which is based on the formation of blue coloured chromogen, when the drug reacts with Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent in alkaline medium. The colored species has an absorption maximum at 760 nm and obey Beer's law in the concentration range 4–22 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The proposed method was tested on the pharmaceutical formulations. The reproducibility, repeatability and precision of method are very good as shown by the low values of standard deviation, standard error of mean, coefficient of variation and % range of error (within 95% confidence limits). The proposed method can be successfully employed for the routine analysis of ezetimibe in tablet dosage forms.

Keywords : Ezetimibe, Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, colorimetry.

Ezetimibe is chemically 1-(4-fluorophenyl)-3(R)-[3-(4-fluorophenyl)-3(S)-hydroxypropyl]-4(S)-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2-azetidinone. It is a selective cholesterol absorption inhibitor used extensively in the treatment of primary hypercholesterolemia, homozygous familial hypercholesterolemia¹⁻³. The therapeutic importance of this drug has prompted the development of many methods for its assay.

A literature of survey revealed a simple UV method⁴, stability indicating HPLC method⁵ and RP-HPLC⁶ method for the determination of ezetimibe in pharmaceutical formulation. The purpose of this investigation was to develop a simple and sensitive visible spectrophotometric method for the quantitation of ezetimibe in pure drug and in pharmaceutical formulations. This method uses the well known reduction reaction involving Folin-Ciocalteu's (FC) reagent and ezetimibe resulting in the formation of a blue chromogen that could be measured at 760 nm.

Experimental

A GBC Cintra 10 double beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer equipped with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used in the present investigation. A Sartorius analytical balance was used. Ezetimibe pure sample was pro-

vided by Zydus Medica, Ahmedabad. 1 N Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was prepared by diluting the 2 N reagent. 1 N Sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by dissolving 40 g of sodium hydroxide pellets in 1 L of distilled water. Standard solution of ezetimibe was prepared by dissolving 100 mg in 100 mL of 1 N sodium hydroxide and was further diluted as appropriate.

Different aliquots of ezetimibe standard solution (1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) from 0.4 to 2.2 mL were transferred into a series of 10 mL standard flasks. To each flask 1.0 mL of FC reagent (1 N) and 2 mL of sodium hydroxide were added and the volume was made up with water. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 760 nm against the reagent blank after 20 min. The calibration curve was then prepared by plotting the absorbance versus concentration of the drug. The concentration of the unknown was read from the calibration graph or computed from the regression equation.

Twenty tablets were weighed and pulverized. A weighed portion of the powder equivalent to 50 mg of ezetimibe was transferred into 50 mL standard flask, 30 mL methanol added and shaken thoroughly for about 20 min. The volume was made up to the mark with water, mixed well and filtered. The tablet extract was subjected

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to analysis using the procedure described above. The nominal content of the tablets was determined from the calibration curve.

Results and discussion

On going through the literature it was found that FC reagent has been used for the development of the spectrophotometric method of drug those containing phenolic group. As ezetimibe contain phenolic group in the structure, so it was decided to develop the new spectrophotometric method of ezetimibe by using FC reagent. FC reagent is the mixture of phosphoric acid, sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate. It is also called as phosphomolybdotungstic acid. The mixed acids in the FC reagent preparation are the final chromogen and involve the following chemical species; $3\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 13\text{WO}_3 \cdot 5\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $3\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 14\text{WO}_3 \cdot 4\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In this developed method, the reduction of FC reagent in the presence of 1 N sodium hydroxide gives a blue coloured chromogen, which may be molybdenum blue or tungsten blue.

Ezetimibe was found to react with Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent in the presence of sodium hydroxide and producing blue color peaking at 760 nm (Fig. 1). The spectrophotometric properties of the colored product as well as the different experimental parameters affecting the color development and its stability were studied carefully and optimized. Such factors were changed individually while the others were kept constant. The factors include concentration of the reagent (FC reagent), time of development of the color, effect of alkalinity of the solution. The influence of the concentrations of FC reagent and sodium hydroxide were studied using different concentrations. It was found that 1 mL of 1 N FC reagent in 2 mL of 1 N sodium hydroxide were optimum volume for complete reaction.

The time of the reaction is an essential part of the experiment. Different time intervals were attempted. It was found that 20 min after addition of FC reagent and

sodium hydroxide was sufficient for reacting its highest absorbance. The absorbance of the color was found to be stable for 3 h.

The absorbance-concentration plot was found to be linear over the range of 4–22 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Linear regression analysis of the data ($n = 10$) gave the following equation :

$$y = 0.0458x - 0.0905$$

where y = absorbance in 1 cm cell, x is the concentration of the drug in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The apparent molar absorptivity was found to be $1.4992 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 1. Ezetimibe scanned in visible range using FC reagent.

Statistical evaluation of the regression line for pharmaceutical formulations has been done. Low values of standard deviation and coefficient of variation point out to the high precision of the proposed method (Table 1). The proposed method was applied to the determination of pure sample of ezetimibe. The proposed method was applied successfully for the determination of ezetimibe in some pharmaceutical preparations adopting the standard addition technique. In case of ezetimibe tablets there was no problem during extraction of ezetimibe with methanol, followed by filtration, and there was no interference from soluble excipients or additives. Drug recovery studies indicate 100 ± 0.04 percentage recovery of the drug.

Table 1. Compilation of results of statistical analysis of commercial formulations of ezetimibe

Tablet	Amount proposed (mg/tab)	Amount found ^a (mg/tab)	SD ^a	COV ^a	SE ^a	t^b	
						Calcd.	Theor.
EZTA	10	9.99 ± 0.0064	0.0080	0.0800	0.0032	1.684	3.365
EZIBLOC	10	9.99 ± 0.0036	0.0045	0.0450	0.0018	2.8849	

^aAverage of six determinations.

^bTheoretical ' t ' values are calculated as 95% confidence level for ($n - 1$) degrees of freedom ' t ' (0.025, 5) = 3.365.

Conclusion :

Ezetimibe has been determined by a specific and simple method. The drug can be determined in the presence of its degradation products, related substances and irrelevant coexisting substances and excipients. It allows determination with good accuracy and precision. It can be readily adapted to routine control analysis of the drug in its formulations.

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